

RoF links in the front-haul network for the future 5G communications

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Abstract: Fronthaul network segment of next generation 5G networks has raised concerns due to expected bandwidth limitations. Among the proposed approaches, Radio over Fiber together with Spatial Division Multiplexing appears as the best suitable solution to implement next generation 5G fronthaul. Optical generation of 5G mobile communication signals in the mmWave spectrum have been explored experimentally. This approach has been used to demonstrate RF optical links of 10km distance with up to 1000Mbps data rate for a BER below 10^{-3} .

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1. Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) systems are growing very rapidly in terms of number of connected users, expected capacity and infrastructure. The total data traffic in the mobile network grew a 74 percent during 2015, reaching 3.7 exabyte per month worldwide. Moreover, an increase of data traffic up to 30.6 exabyte per month is expected by 2020 [1]. Thus, the vast majority of all that traffic coming from mobile devices have to be routed through the backhaul and into the core network, this will provoke a bottleneck in terms of bandwidth capacity. This trend is also applicable to datacenters and fronthaul networks (see Fig. 1) [2]. It is expected that new communication scenarios will require to scale bandwidth capacity by a factor of 1000. This new emerging scenarios include 5G mobile communications [3,4] and Internet of Things (IoT) [5] both supported by mobile networks using the millimeter wave (mmWave) spectrum and size-reduced cells (femto-cells). Even though reducing the cell size enables a better spectrum efficiency and higher bandwidth, it will also incur in cost increase and network management problems. Thus, scaling to the mmWave (~30GHz) permits to access a higher potential bandwidth, but the cost of transceivers increase, and as they are located next to radiation elements, the maintenance cost also increase. On top of that, traditional copper based network will not be capable of provide the expected bandwidth of 5G. For that reason is crucial to implement fronthaul networks based on optical links. Furthermore, bandwidth requirements will be also difficult to meet with traditional Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) techniques. In this sense, Spatial Division Multiplexing (SDM) together with Radio over Fiber (RoF) technology has been recently considered as the ideal solution for the fronthaul. Firstly, RoF permits to centralize the management of the network on a Central Office optimizing the use of resources. Secondly, RoF require less bandwidth and less data treatment in the base stations, leading to a reduction of operational costs. Finally, SDM provides a new orthogonality level to multiplex enabling bandwidth scaling [6,7].

Fig. 1 Fronthaul segment of the mobile communication network.

2. Analog optical links

Our work is focused on the study and experimental demonstration of RoF links following the scheme of Fig. 2. Firstly two tones separated 30GHz are generated modulating a laser using LiNbO3 Mach-Zehnder modulator biased in the null point and a fixed RF oscillator of 15GHz as modulating signal (see spectrum on Fig. 2). The two tones are then modulated in dual side band by a RF signal generator centered around 3.5GHz, emulating the RF transmitted signals of mobile communications. Another LiNbO3 Mach-Zehnder modulator was used to modulated the two tones, in this case biased in the quadrature point. The associated spectrum of the generated signal is depicted in Fig. 2. This signal is then propagated through a 10km long single mode fiber (SMF). The received signal is, then converted to mmWave domain in a photodiode. The beating centered a 26.5GHz is filtered and send to the signal analyzer. The considered RF signals included QPSK and M-QAM up to 256QAM, with a maximum symbol rate of 500MSps. For each modulation format the maximum symbol rate was obtained for bit error rate (BER) below 10^{-3} . 16MSps transmission was obtained for 256QAM case (128Mbps). In the case of 128QAM a maximum symbol rate of 27MSps (189Mbps) was obtained. 45MSps was the maximum sybol rate for 64QAM (270Mbps). For 32QAM transmission up to 55MSps (275Mbps) was possible. 150MSps data transmission was possible for 16QAM (750Mbps). Finally, in the QPSK case the maximum symbol rate was limited by the equipment, reaching the 500MSps (1000Mbps).

Fig. 1 Experimental setup.

3. Conclusions

Optical generation of RF mobile communication signals in the mmWave spectrum have been explored experimentally. This approach has been use to demonstrate RF optical links of 10km distance with up to 1000Mbps data rate for a BER below 10^{-3} .

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